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Without cytomegalovirus infection, no psoriasis vulgaris

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Psoriasis vulgaris (PV) is a chronic skin disease which is leading to a substantial burden for human societies and individuals. The potential relationship between cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection and PV has been re-investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

The study of Kirby et al. has been re-investigated. The data of the study of Kirby et al. are of restricted value, but still of use. These data support a clear relationship.

CONCLUSION:

Without a cytomegalovirus infection, no psoriasis vulgaris.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Psoriasis vulgaris; Necessary condition; Conditio sine qua non; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The ultimate pathogenesis of psoriasis vulgaris (PV) is unclear. Still, there is some evidence suggesting that PV is a T-cell mediated ¹ disease triggered by an infectious agent. Although there is circumstantial evidence that viral antigens may be important in the pathogenesis of psoriasis, various external (stress, seasonal factors, infection, sun exposure, β -blockers and other) and internal risk factors (obesity, diabetes mellitus et cetera) ² are attributed to psoriasis vulgaris. The worldwide incidence and prevalence of psoriasis vulgaris ³ · ⁴ varies from country to country, however, psoriasis can appear at any age. It has been found that the prevalence in children ranged from 0 % (Taiwan) to 2.1 % (Italy), and in adults from 0.91 % (United States) to 8.5 % (Norway). ⁵ Biologicals like Etanercept, Infliximab, Adalimumab, Certolizumab, Ustekinumab, Secukinumab, Ixekizumab, Brodalumab, Guselkumab, Tildrakizumab and potentially Risankizumab are used to treat PV. It is known that tumour necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) is able to mediate host-resistance against micro-organisms and inhibits at the end CMV replication. Especially, serum TNF- α is found to be elevated during acute CMV-infections. ⁶ Unfortunately, tumour necrosis factor alpha is a very powerful cytokine with a very 'dark side' too. TNF- α is involved causally in various pathological processes. A successful therapy of PV with TNF- α blocking agents like etanercept ⁷ · ⁸ et cetera is appropriate enough to indicate a certain level of evidence that CMV might play a central role in the pathogenesis of psoriasis vulgaris. The relationship between CMV and PV is investigated.

¹Valdimarsson H, Baker BS, Jónsdóttir I, Powles A, Fry L. Psoriasis: a T-cell-mediated autoimmune disease induced by streptococcal superantigens? *Immunol Today*. 1995 Mar;16(3):145-9. doi: 10.1016/0167-5699(95)80132-4. PMID: 7718088.

²Kamiya K, Kishimoto M, Sugai J, Komine M, Ohtsuki M. Risk Factors for the Development of Psoriasis. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2019 Sep 5;20(18):4347. doi: 10.3390/ijms20184347. PMID: 31491865; PMCID: PMC6769762.

³Parisi R, Symmons DP, Griffiths CE, Ashcroft DM; Identification and Management of Psoriasis and Associated Comorbidity (IMPACT) project team. Global epidemiology of psoriasis: a systematic review of incidence and prevalence. *J Invest Dermatol*. 2013 Feb;133(2):377-85. doi: 10.1038/jid.2012.339. Epub 2012 Sep 27. PMID: 23014338.

⁴Michalek IM, Loring B, John SM. A systematic review of worldwide epidemiology of psoriasis. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2017 Feb;31(2):205-212. doi: 10.1111/jdv.13854. Epub 2016 Aug 30. PMID: 27573025.

⁵c. I. Parisi et al.

⁶Haerter G, Manfras BJ, de Jong-Hesse Y, Wilts H, Mertens T, Kern P, Schmitt M. Cytomegalovirus retinitis in a patient treated with anti-tumor necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy for rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004 Nov 1;39(9):e88-94. doi: 10.1086/425123. Epub 2004 Oct 11. PMID: 15494900.

⁷Hung YM, Lin L, Chen CM, Chiou JY, Wang YH, Wang PY, Wei JC. The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2017 Jun 28;12(6):e0179081. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0179081. PMID: 28658301; PMCID: PMC5489160.

⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. *International Journal Of Current Science Research*. Volume: 6; Issue: 1; January-2020; pp 1912-1938. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Kirby et al.

Kirby et al. ⁹ investigated 29 psoriasis vulgaris patients for the presence of serum immunoglobulin G (IgG) to CMV. Kirby et al. found that “Twenty-one of 29 (72%) patients had IgG antibodies to CMV, compared with 50% in ... control population (18)”. Kirby et al. concluded that there is no statistically significant relationship between CMV infection, as assessed by the presence or absence of serum IgG to CMV, and psoriasis vulgaris. Unfortunately, it is not completely clear whether the control group consisted of 18 patient. Nonetheless, the data of Kirby et al. are of some use for further investigations.

⁹Kirby B, Al-Jiffri O, Cooper RJ, Corbitt G, Klapper PE, Griffiths CE. Investigation of cytomegalovirus and human herpes viruses 6 and 7 as possible causative antigens in psoriasis. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2000 Nov-Dec;80(6):404-6. doi: 10.1080/000155500300012738. PMID: 11243630.

Table 1. The relationship between CMV IgG and Psoriasis vulgaris (Study of Kirby et al. , 2000).

		Psoriasis vulgaris		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	21	9	30
	NO	8	9	17
		29	18	47

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,22675952$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,10744145
p (SINE) = 0,82978723
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,72413793
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,52941176

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,10744145
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 3,76
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 2,21
P Value (SINE) = 0,15651467

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (21 / 30) \times 100 = 70,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (9 / 30) \times 100 = 30,00 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (8 / 17) \times 100 = 47,06 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (9 / 17) \times 100 = 52,94 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (21 / 29) \times 100 = 72,41 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (8 / 29) \times 100 = 27,59 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (9 / 18) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (9 / 18) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (30 / 47) \times 100 = 63,83 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (17 / 47) \times 100 = 36,17 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (29 / 47) \times 100 = 61,70 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (18 / 47) \times 100 = 38,30 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,48750000
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,44827586

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 2,62500000
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,13448276

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,25531915
p(IOI)= 0,02127660

The original data as presented by table 1 are very unfair and potentially biased. Nonetheless, the relative risk with RR (necessary condition) = 1,4875 and with RR (sufficient condition) = 1,4482 indicates a cause effect relationship between CMV and PV. Therefore, we assume a fair study design and obtain the following data presented by table 2.

Table 2. The relationship between CMV IgG and Psoriasis vulgaris (Study of Kirby et al., 2000 (fictive control group)).

		Psoriasis vulgaris		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	21	29	50
	NO	8	29	37
		29	58	87

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,21371868$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,03773168
p (SINE) = 0,90804598
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,72413793
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,78378378

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,03773168
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 1,73
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 2,21
P Value (SINE) = 0,08785291

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (21 / 50) \times 100 = 42,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (29 / 50) \times 100 = 58,00 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (8 / 37) \times 100 = 21,62 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (29 / 37) \times 100 = 78,38 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (21 / 29) \times 100 = 72,41 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (8 / 29) \times 100 = 27,59 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (29 / 58) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (29 / 58) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (50 / 87) \times 100 = 57,47 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (37 / 87) \times 100 = 42,53 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (29 / 87) \times 100 = 33,33 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (58 / 87) \times 100 = 66,67 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,94250000
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,44827586

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 2,62500000
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,26000000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,09195402
p(IOI)= 0,24137931

The study design is more or less fair (p(IOU)= 0,09195402) while the relative risk with RR (necessary condition) = 1,9425 and with RR (sufficient condition) = 1,4482 indicates a cause effect relationship between CMV and PV.

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹⁰ too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 3. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>d</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

¹⁰Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution¹¹. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

¹¹Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the populations distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.6. Sample size

In scientific practice, the truth is not known from the very beginning, but often need to be discovered in arduous detail work. Many times, scientist base inferences on statistical tests applied to a random sample drawn from a population. In this process of insight, there are some mistakes that can occur. Especially, a null hypothesis which is true can incorrectly be rejected and the either way. A null hypothesis which is false can incorrectly be accepted. However, one key aspect when designing an experiment or a clinical study et cetera, is the calculation of an appropriate sample size. A sample size is the number of experimental units or measurements (i.e. the number of patients in a medical study) et cetera needed to be included into a study in order to answer a certain research question. Therefore, an accurate pre-study calculation of the sample size ¹² is of great importance. Nonetheless, it is worthy of attention that methods to calculate the sample size which are explained in statistical textbooks in more detail are prone to errors and changes in the selected parameters can lead to significant differences in the sample size. In fact, our experience so far has taught us, that a sample size which is too small, is tending to make it impossible to detect any difference or effect. In complete contrast to a small sample size, a sample that is larger than necessary might be a better representative of a certain population and may provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, a sample that is too large may amplify differences and induce a waste of time and money. The issue of sample size is more or less not as simple as is often desired or assumed. Thus far and for illustration purposes only, let us suppose that a small study is investigating the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human being alive. Only three subjects were investigated, the following data were obtained and published.

Table 4. Gaseous oxygen and human being alive

		Human being alive B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	TRUE	1	1	2
	FALSE	0	1	1
		1	2	3

Are the results of such a study completely irrelevant? Under normal circumstances, our confidence into a relationship identified is running high, parallel with an increasing sample size. In contrast to a very large sample size, even a study with a very small sample size ($N = 3$) or even one single study is capable of identifying a fundamental relationship i.e. between gaseous oxygen and human life, it depends as always on the concrete circumstances. Human experience teaches us however that the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life as established before is true even if the sample size of the study presented is very small. As is well known, it is rarely possible to study the entire population. Nonetheless, further studies despite a larger sample size must be able to confirm the relationship established before in principle, independently of any potential difficulties.

¹²Hickey GL, Grant SW, Dunning J, Siepe M. Statistical primer: sample size and power calculations-why, when and how? *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg.* 2018 Jul 1;54(1):4-9. doi: 10.1093/ejcts/ezy169. PMID: 29757369; PMCID: PMC6005113.

Type I Error (Alpha)

The type I error is also called alpha or the significance level or the P Value and represents the chance or the probability to decide that two groups investigated differ while in reality these two groups do not differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-positive conclusion. Under usual circumstances, alpha is fixed at 0.05, which indicates that a researcher desires a less than 5% chance of drawing a false-positive conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because positive. The P Value is the probability obtained of incorrectly accepting the alternate hypothesis. The P Value is compared to the the significance level α to determine whether the result is statistically significant. The lower the P Value, the lower the probability of obtaining that result if a null hypothesis were true.

Type I and type II errors

Type I error: A true null hypothesis is rejected. **Type II error:** A false null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 1. Today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error.

Power (1-Beta)

The type II error is also called beta and represents the chance or the probability to decide that the two groups investigated do not differ (no difference), while in reality these two groups do differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-negative conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because negative. Usually, beta is set at a level of 0.20. In other words, a researcher desires a less than 20% chance of a false-negative conclusion. Nonetheless, for the calculation of the sample size, it is necessary to consider the following relationship.

$$\beta + \text{power} = 1 \quad (15)$$

Consequently, power is the complement of beta, i.e. $\text{power} = 1 - \beta$. Thus far, if beta is 0.20, then the power is 0.80 or 80%. The power indicates the probability or the chance to avoid a false-negative conclusion or, in other words, the probability to detect a specified effect, assumed that the same really exists.

What is very interesting is that today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error excludes the possibility of a joint distribution between Type I error and Type II error, as demonstrated by figure ¹³ 1. In other words, theoretically, it appears not to be possible that a null-hypothesis is false in reality (α) and that a statistical test tell us at the same time that a null-hypothesis is false (β) too. In the long run, this shortcoming may turn out to be unsustainable.

Table 5. Today's relationship between α and β

		R E S E A R C H		
		H ₀ is TRUE	H _A is TRUE	
R E A L I T Y	H ₀ is TRUE	$1 - \alpha$	α	1
	H _A is TRUE	β	$1 - \beta$	1
		$1 - \alpha + \beta$	$1 + \alpha - \beta$	2

¹³Serdar CC, Cihan M, Yücel D, Serdar MA. Sample size, power and effect size revisited: simplified and practical approaches in pre-clinical, clinical and laboratory studies. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2021 Feb 15;31(1):010502. doi: 10.11613/BM.2021.010502. Epub 2020 Dec 15. PMID: 33380887; PMCID: PMC7745163.

3. Results

3.1. Theorem. Without cytomegalovirus infection, no psoriasis vulgaris

Theorem 1 (Without cytomegalovirus infection, no psoriasis vulgaris).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Without CMV infection, no psoriasis vulgaris is true. ($p(\text{SINE}) = 1.$)

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

*Without CMV infection, no psoriasis vulgaris is **not** true. ($p(\text{SINE}) < 1.$)*

Proof by the study of Kirby et al. The data of the study of Kirby et al. ¹⁴ are statistically analysed (see table 1). The sample size (N =47) is very small, while the data provided are very unfair ($p(\text{IOU})=0.2553191$). Nonetheless, the same data are of some use for our purposes. The causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0.2267595$; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0.10744145) and does not contradict a necessary condition relationship. The probability of a necessary condition relationship ($p(\text{SINE})$) between CMV and PV is $p(\text{SINE}) = 0.82978723$ and with P Value = 0.10744145 not statistically significant. Nonetheless, the chi-square values or a necessary condition relationship with 3.76 and with 2.21 are less than 3.84 and not significant. Based on the chi-square distribution, we cannot find any difference between the necessary condition relationship identified within the sample and the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship within the population. Besides of the very inappropriate study design, the null-hypothesis need to be accepted.

Without cytomegalovirus infection, **no** psoriasis vulgaris (Chi-square < 3.84).

□

Under conditions of a fair study design (see table 2), the necessary condition relationship between CMV and PV is significant and much stronger ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0.90804598$; P Value = 0.03773168).

¹⁴Kirby B, Al-Jiffri O, Cooper RJ, Corbitt G, Klapper PE, Griffiths CE. Investigation of cytomegalovirus and human herpes viruses 6 and 7 as possible causative antigens in psoriasis. Acta Derm Venereol. 2000 Nov-Dec;80(6):404-6. doi: 10.1080/000155500300012738. PMID: 11243630.

3.2. CMV and treatment

A treatment of a CMV infection can be initiated, supervised and monitored by a medical specialist experienced with the drugs suggested as follows. The scientific justification for the proposed medications can be found somewhere else.¹⁵

Table 6. CMV infection: Additional therapy

Data:	Name	First name	Birthday	Place of residence	Phone	E-Mail	Approved by
Drug	Immunoglobulin	Lefunomide	Etoricoxib	Etanercept	Valaciclovir	Atorvastatin	Cimetidin
Dosage	1 g per kg i.v. qd	10 mg qd or 20 mg p.o. qd	30 mg or 90 mg p.o. qd	10 mg or 25 mg or 50 mg s.c.	2 g p. o. qid	80 mg qd	800 mg qd
Month:							
Day:							
1	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
2		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
3	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
4		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
5	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
6		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
7		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
8		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
9		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
10		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
11		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
12		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
13		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
14		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
15		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
16		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
17		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
18		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
19		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
20		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
21		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
22		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
23		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
24		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
25		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
26		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
27		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
28		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
29		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
30		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
31		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0

¹⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?. *Causation*, 18(11), 5–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7567432>

4. Discussion

The data of the study of Kirby et al.¹⁶ should be treated with considerable caution. The sample size is small and these data are potentially biased. However, the small sample size can but need not compromise the conclusions drawn from this study.¹⁷ Bearing this point in mind, it is indeed difficult to establish a generally valid relationship between CMV and PV under these circumstances. Nonetheless and despite all the adversities, we have to face the fact that even under very unfavourable conditions, the data published by Kirby et al. provide some evidence of a necessary condition relationship between CMV and PV (Chi-square < 3.84). These circumstances justify the realisation of a very precise investigation in order to verify a possible relationship between CMV and PV. However, as long as there is no contradiction from studies to the contrary, we may in good faith come to the following and preliminary conclusion.

5. Conclusion

Given the above and because of lack of evidence to the contrary, it is provisionally concluded that

Without CMV infection, no psoriasis vulgaris.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

¹⁶Kirby B, Al-Jiffri O, Cooper RJ, Corbitt G, Klapper PE, Griffiths CE. Investigation of cytomegalovirus and human herpes viruses 6 and 7 as possible causative antigens in psoriasis. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2000 Nov-Dec;80(6):404-6. doi: 10.1080/000155500300012738. PMID: 11243630.

¹⁷Faber J, Fonseca LM. How sample size influences research outcomes. *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2014 Jul-Aug;19(4):27-9. doi: 10.1590/2176-9451.19.4.027-029.ebo. PMID: 25279518; PMCID: PMC4296634.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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